

Local Newton's Second Law and Momentum Wave in Quantum Mechanics

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Ehrenfest's theorem: $d [\int dx W^*(x) i/\hbar d/dx W(x)] / dt = [\int dx W^*(x) (d/dx V(x)) W(x)]$ has the appearance of a "kind of average" Newton's second law, but it is nonlocal and includes, it seems, density i.e. the p average portion is $\int p P(p/x) P(x)$ where $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$. Thus, there are changes in average local momentum as well as density as one moves from point to point (similar to $d/dt (mv) = (dm/dt) v + m dv/dt$) in classical physics. In this note, we attempt to consider Newton's second law at a local point x for a stochastic system (i.e. a p distribution $f(p,x)$). We also investigate if the "wave" structure $f(p,x) = \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ follows from this approach.

Ehrenfest's Theorem

Ehrenfest's theorem (1) is often used to demonstrate that "on density average" quantum mechanics may have the same form as Newton's second law for a sharply peaked wavefunction i.e. a localized particle. The theorem, however, is based on an integral over all space and seems to deal with changes in momentum as well as density. It is based on:

$$d/dt [\int dx W^*(x) A(t) W(x)] = 1/i\hbar \int dx W^*(x) [A, H] W(x) + \int dx W^*(x) (dA(t)/dt) W(x) \quad ((1))$$

For $A(t) = \text{momentum operator} = -i\hbar d/dx$ (no t dependence), one obtains $d/dt [\int dx W^*(x) p W(x)] = \int dx W^*(x) (-dV(x)/dx) W(x) \quad ((2))$

In this note, we argue one may immediately consider a local description of momentum which does not require integration or the presence of $W^*(x)W(x)$, spatial density. We note that:

$$d/dt [\int dx W^*(x) (Poperator) W(x)] = d/dt [\int dx \sum_{\pi} P(\pi/x) P(x)] \quad ((3))$$

Where $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(\pi/x) = \exp(ipix)/W(x) \quad ((4))$

Thus, d/dt acts on both spatial density and the local probability to have a p at point x . This is somewhat analogous to the classical: $d/dt (mv) = v dm/dt + m dv/dt$.

Local Momentum Considerations

In previous notes, we considered the idea of a momentum distribution at point x i.e. $P(p/x) = f(p,x)$ where $\sum_{\pi} P(\pi/x) = 1$. For a classical system, there is a fixed p at x (or $\pm p$ for a

bound system), but not a distribution. We then “enforced” conservation of energy at each point x :

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m f(p,x)] + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

Equation ((4)) is completely local. It assumes a quantum particle in a momentum state p has a defined kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$ and then averages over different possible p 's which exist at different times at the same point x .

In previous notes, we did not consider Newton's second law directly at point x to see if it is consistent with the idea of kinetic energy. For example, for a classical system, one may argue: $d/dt p(x)$ depends strictly on a function $G(x)$ (related to force). If m is constant, then the change of velocity in time is directly related to its change in space i.e. $v(x(t))$. Thus, $d/dt v(x) = dv/dx dx/dt = G(x)$ or $v dv = dx G(x)$. Integrating yields the kinetic energy form $\frac{1}{2} v^2$, one need only insert m (as a postulate) to obtain kinetic energy. How does deal with a stochastic quantum system where one has a distribution of p at x ?

We suggest that for a given p_i in the interval x to $x+\Delta x$, there will be a “hit” from a potential adding a momentum p_j to the particle with probability $a_j(x+\Delta x/2)$. $A_j(x)$ depends on the nature of the potential function.

On average, the force hit may occur in the middle of the interval $x+\Delta x/2$. Thus, a given p_i appears at x with probability $f(p_i,x)$ and may react with a p_j from the potential (i.e. change to p_i+p_j both vectors) with a probability $a_j(x)$.

Thus, $d/dt p_i$ would be given by:

$$\text{Sum over } j \text{ } [(p_j+p_i) - p_i] a_j(x+\Delta x/2) [p_j+p_i + p_i]/2m f(p_i,x) a_j(x+\Delta x/2) \quad ((5))$$

Here $(p_j+p_i)/2m$ is the average velocity in the region of Δx . We have used $dv/dt = dv/dx dx/dt$ for each p_i and set dx/dt equal to the average $.5(v_j+v_i)$.

To consider all p_i one sums ((5)) over i . This yields:

$$d/dt p(x) \text{ local} = \text{sum } i,j \text{ } [(p_j+p_i)^2 - p_i^2] (\frac{1}{2}m) f(p_i,x) a_j(x+\Delta x/2) = \text{Sum } i,j \text{ } (p_j+p_i)^2 f(p_i,x) a_j(x+\Delta x/2) - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(p_i,x) p_i^2/2m \quad ((6))$$

Thus, one has: Function $(x+\Delta x/2)$ - KE local $(x) = d/dt p(x)$ local. Kinetic energy emerges without the introduction of an integral $v dv$. In order to have KE local $(x+\Delta x) - KE$ local (x) , $\text{Sum over } j \text{ } (p_j+p_i)^2 f(p_i,x) a_j(x+\Delta x/2)$ should equal KE local $(x+\Delta x)$.

For a bound state with $a_j(-x)=a_j(x)$, it seems that KE local $(x+\Delta x) - KE$ local $(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } k^2/2m a_k(x+\Delta x/2)$. Thus, the hit from the potential (in the average case) adds a momentum of k and a kinetic energy of $k^2/2m$ to each p momentum state. (This is an average because forward and backward motion have been considered to eliminate $p_i \cdot k$.)

This also seems to imply: $\sum_{i,j} (p_j + p_i)^2 f(p_i, x) a_j(x + \Delta x/2) = \sum_k f(p_k, x + \Delta x) p_k^2 / 2m$ ((7))

Thus, $f(p_i, x) a_j(x + \Delta x/2)$ seems to be equivalent to $f(p_k, x + \Delta x/2)$ where $k=i+j$. This seems to indicate a similar form for $f(p_i, x)$ and $a_j(x + \Delta x/2)$. In fact, $C(p) a^{p_i + p_j}$ appears to be a solution in terms of momentum p . What about x ? One may argue it should also have linearity in x and that $f(p_i, x)$ may actually be $f(p_i, x + \Delta x/2)$. Also, one may argue that different x values only add a phase, like with p . (In a previous note, we argued that this is similar to the idea of a loss of information in a statistical theory.)

Then, $C(p) a^{p x b}$ is a possible solution, with b being a constant. A real positive b seems problematic because it would favour huge p . A real negative b is also problematic for a periodic potential or for one in which momentum increases. Thus, choosing b as a pure imaginary number, namely “ i ” may provide a solution. Thus, it seems the momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$ arises as a solution of a stochastic, local Newton’s second law problem. Furthermore, it seems that one is using a Fourier series decomposition approach. This stochastic Newton’s second law problem is consistent with local conservation of energy i.e. ((1)). If $f(p, x)$ is proportional to $\exp(ipx)$, then a normalization constant is required, namely $W(x) = \sum_p \exp(ipx) a_p$ where a_p is the weight of each p which does not change with x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, unlike the approach used in Ehrenfest’s theorem, we consider the application of Newton’s law to a stochastic distribution of momentum at a point x . We find that d/dt applied to this distribution leads to $\text{Function}(x + \Delta x) - KE(x)$ and conclude that $\text{Function}(x + \Delta x) = KE(x + \Delta x)$. Thus, conservation of energy seems to emerge. We further argue that the form of $\text{Function}(x + \Delta x)$ contains $f(p_i, x) a_j(p_j)$ where $f(p, x)$ is the probability of p in the momentum distribution and $a_j(p_j)$ the probability of a momentum increase of p_j by the force. This leads to a possible solution of $f(p, x)$ of the form of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the momentum wave in quantum mechanics.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ehrenfest_theorem